

Automated Smoking Zone with Fire Detection Monitoring and Alerting

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Abstract— A smoke detector alarm with fire detection alarm protection device that automatically detects smoke and fire also gives us warning. Within the proposed framework, a smoke locator upon faculties smoke actuates its alert, and fire finder upon faculties fire actuates its caution, sends a voltage flag to all other smoke detectors and fire detector in the vicinity. This low voltage signal activates the individual relays in the other smoke detectors and fire detector causing them to emit a tone that alerts residents that one of the smoke locators faculties smoke Fire locator identify fire. In this framework the transmitter and recipient are introduced in a unit and the require for a base is killed. The individual smoke detectors and fire detector are equipped with all the electronics required to both send and receive signals. They can be introduced by a mortgage holder fair as they would a ordinary smoke detector. The proposed design is aiming to have Cost efficient system, Compact design, easily expandable, Simple to install, Replaceable compo. They can be introduced by a property holder fair as they would a typical smoke detector. The proposed plan is pointing to have taken a toll effective framework, Compact plan, effortlessly expandable, Straightforward to introduce, Replaceable components.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The fire prevention technologies are constantly innovating along with the growing science and technology, because fire is a serious threat to human life and properties. The appearance of the fire is often accompanied by the generation of smoke. Actually in the early stages of the fire, a lot of smoke is produced due to the fuel temperature and combustion is not high enough. Smoke cannot be covered by a large area, and the mobility is relatively high. If the fire can be detected before the occurrence of fire and sent an early warning to the nearest fire station, the occurrence of fire and a large area spreading of fire can be maintained a strategic distance from so as to diminish people's fabric and budgetary damage. There are a number of fires and smoke location frameworks are accessible these days. But all these systems provide a warning signal on the building premises only. At that point the fire discovery was done basically by visual assessment and affirmation by a human being and the fire station as it were educated when somebody make a call to the fire station. A real time fire and smoke detection system can solve this issue and inform to LCD display. This system is cheaper compared to all currently available systems in market. This genuine time fire and smoke discovery framework is planned to identify the fire and smoke at the early arrange and inform the closest fire station through a thrust notification. The notice contains the fire or smoke caution and the area information's. Arduinio UNO processor is used in this system.

II. SYSTEM COMPONENTS AND TYPES

System is implemented fire and smoke detection and alarm. It comprises of the taking after components to co-ordinated the framework objective: Arduino UNO [1, 2], Smoke sensor MQ-2, Buzzer, and the Fluid Precious stone show LCD.

A. Arduino UNO

Arduino Uno is microcontroller board and based on the Atmel's ATmega328 microcontroller. "Uno" means one in Italian and the uno board is the latest in a series of USB (Universal Serial Bus). The Arduino Uno board has a 16 MHz ceramic resonator, a USB connection, a power jack, an ICSP header, a reset button, 6 analog inputs and 14 digital

input/output pins (of which 6 can be used as PWM outputs). The board has 32 KB flash memory of which 0.5 KB is used by boot-loader, 2 KB of SRAM, 1 KB of EEPROM and 16 MHz clock speed. The Arduino system offers a set of analog and digital pins that can be integrated to many other boards and circuits which absolutely have different functions in a design. Arduino board provides a USB serial communication interface for loading the codes from computer. To do the codes, Arduino has prepared its own software called integrated development environment (IDE) which completely supports C and C++ programming languages [1]-[2].

Figure 1: Arduino UNO microcontroller and MQ-6 Sensor

B. MQ-6 Smoke and IR Sensor

The MQ arrangement of gas sensors utilize a little radiator interior with an electro-chemical sensor appeared in figure 1. They are touchy for a run of gasses and are utilized inside at room temperature. The yield is an analog flag and can be perused with an analog input of a PIC microcontroller. The MQ-6 Gas Sensor module is valuable for gas spillage identifying in domestic and industry. It is profoundly delicate within the discovery of the nearness LPG, butane, propane, methane, liquor, hydrogen and smoke. A few modules have a built-in variable resistor to alter the affectability of the sensor. It was utilized in this investigate work for the discovery of LPG and smoke within the building. The resistance of the sensor is diverse depending on the type of the gas. The smoke sensor encompasses a built in potentiometer that permits you to alter the sensor affectability concurring to how precise you need to identify gas [5, 7].

```
void setup() {
  pinMode(buzzer, OUTPUT);
  pinMode(smokeA0, INPUT);
  Serial.begin(9600);
}

void loop() {
  int analogSensor = analogRead(smokeA0);
  Serial.print("Pin A0: ");
  Serial.println(analogSensor);
  if (analogSensor > 400) tone(buzzer, 1000, 200);
  else noTone(buzzer); delay(1000);
}
```

C. Liquid Crystal Display Unit (LCD)

This device includes a 16×2character LCD display. The liquid crystal display is connected via a variable resistor; The

variable resistor (10kΩ) is used to adjust the brightness of the LCD screen. The LCD displays the system status when gas is detected or when a flame is detected through various sensors installed in the system.

The following program will print temperature and relative humidity values on a 16×2character LCD display [8].

Figure 2: Liquid crystal display unit (LCD)

D. Buzzer

Buzzer is a mechanical, electromechanical, magnetic, electromagnetic, electro acoustic or piezoelectric acoustic signaling device. The piezoelectric buzzer can be controlled by an oscillating electronic circuit or another audio signal source. A click, beep, or chime may indicate that the button has been pressed. It consists of a number of switches or sensors connected to a controller to determine whether a button has been pressed or whether a predetermined time has passed. It typically illuminates a light on the appropriate button or panel and emits a warning in the form of a continuous or intermittent buzzing or beeping sound [8].

Figure 3: Buzzer

III. RELATED WORK

This section covers topics related to real-time smoke and fire detection systems. They provide a sample of problems suitable for the application of real-time smoke and fire detection systems. The references are summarized below.

A. Need for wireless fire detection systems using IOT [1]: The connection of physical devices integrated with electronic components, software and sensors, capable of collecting data necessary data from the environment and sending this data over the Internet is called IOT. Fire detection includes all the techniques and procedures that ensure early detection of fire. There are three main types: Smoke Detection, Flame Detection, and Temperature Detection. The automatic fire detection system will perform real-time monitoring.

Automatic fire alarm systems are designed mainly for high-rise buildings. To quickly extinguish fires, a large number of detectors are deployed in buildings to periodically measure the concentration or temperature of smoke. There are many techniques that we have used to detect fires, such as fire detection using sensors, image processing and video surveillance technology.

B. Unified Smoke and Fire Detection for Smart Surveillance Systems [2]: This article explains how to unify smoke and fire detection algorithms by consolidating common steps into one processing workflow only. Smoke detection and flame detection can be performed using color probability, boundary roughness, edge density, and area variation filtering procedures. Preliminary results obtained show that by treating smoke and flame in parallel, the processing time can be reduced. The results obtained from the unified processing unit can be used as input for various tasks of the intelligent monitoring system.

C. Design and construction of a smoke early warning system [3]: In this article, the author proposes a simple hardware design, including different fire sensors that allow each user to use this wireless fire safety system. The challenges in designing nodes with different types of fire sensors are discussed and methods to overcome this problem are analyzed. The system is interfaced with a variety of sensors to detect various fire sources such as gas leaks, smoke and heat. This circuit is completely controlled by a PIC microcontroller.

All sensors and detectors are connected to a PIC microcontroller. The PIC microcontroller will periodically monitor all connected sensors and when a security issue is detected, a notification will be sent wirelessly to the PC's central monitoring station. The distance must be between 300m indoors and 1500m outdoors when using zigbee. Gas, light, smoke, infrared, temperature and humidity sensors can also be interfaced with this microcontroller to detect abnormal fire conditions in the environment in any possible way. An ARM7 based microcontroller can also be used to build such systems.

D. Developing an early fire detection system using Arduino UNO [4]: The fire alarm system proposed in this article uses only affordable components. The fire alarm system monitors in real time. When a fire is detected, it will automatically take photos and display them on the screen. When the output of related sensors such as temperature, humidity, CO2 and fire exceeds the threshold limit, the controller starts sending signals to the GSM module. The main feature of this system is the ability to send remote alerts whenever fire or smoke is detected. The system can also alert users through the GSM module.

IV. METHODOLOGY

In this system, the fire and smoke detection system is designed and developed using an Arduino controller. The Arduino controller acts as the main controller of the system, the smoke sensor is used to detect smoke and the infrared sensor is used to detect fire. The horn acts as an alarm. The

general fire detection and alarm system and block diagram are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Smoke & Fire Detection Alarm Systems

1. Arduino fire alarm system is an important system for industrial as well as civil purposes. Whenever fire or smoke is detected, it will immediately alert the user about the fire through the GSM module.

Figure 5: Flow Chart

Figure 5 shows the hardware of this box consists of a gas sensor, an Arduino microcontroller, which is connected to the Arduino via a relay module to control it. A fire alarm system consists of several devices that work together to detect and warn people through visual and audible devices of the presence of smoke, fire, carbon monoxide or other dangerous situations. The spread of fire and smoke in a building can be influenced by many different factors such as the shape, size, layout and intended use of the building.

If the detector detects smoke or heat, or if someone activates a broken window unit, a siren will sound to warn others in the building that there may be a fire and they can give up.

CONCLUSION

This article presents the design and implementation of a reliable and cost-effective automatic fire alarm system. Fire detectors use many different sensors, typically smoke sensors and temperature and humidity sensors. The sensor input data is connected to the Arduino controller. LCD screen, Buzzer

connected to Arduino to display output results. Fire alarm when there is a fire alarm and LCD screen displays fire detection status. This system can be applied in residential, office and hotel places. With this system, security is guaranteed. The system can perform various parameter measurements for early detection of building fires. There should be at least two or three smoke detectors and detectors in your home.

You must install smoke detectors and detectors on each floor of the house. Always equip smoke detectors and fire alarm systems in your home to ensure your own safety. The benefits of the system can contribute to early response, saving lives and property. It can also protect us and our homes.

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